

IMPLEMENTATION OF ALGORITHMS FOR FIXED DEPOSIT USING SMART CONTRACT

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Abstract : The implementation of a framework for a fixed deposit system using smart contract in Remix IDE provides a secure and efficient method for managing fixed deposit accounts. This system utilizes the Ethereum blockchain, which ensures transparency, security, and immutability of data. The Smart Contract is coded using the Solidity programming language and designed using the Remix Integrated Development Environment. The framework allows for the creation of new fixed deposit accounts, depositing funds, and withdrawing the funds. Additionally, the system implements interest calculations and provides notifications to the account owners. This framework provides a reliable and automated fixed deposit system, improving the functionality of financial institutions.

IndexTerms - Blockchain, Ethereum, SHA 256, Remix IDE, Smart Contract, Solidity.

1. INTRODUCTION-

The use of blockchain technology has revolutionized various industries. One area where blockchain can be extensively applied is finance. Financial institutions across the globe are already interested in blockchain technology, with many exploring ways to implement this technology within their systems [1]. One of the most significant areas of digital modernization in finance has been the implementation of smart contracts in the blockchain. Smart contracts can automate a myriad of financial transactions, reduce human error, and enhance security [2]. Fixed deposit accounts are a popular investment option for financial institutions and individuals. These types of accounts offer higher interest rates than traditional savings accounts. While fixed deposit accounts are beneficial for depositors, managing them can become difficult for financial institutions. This is where blockchain technology and smart contracts can be leveraged to make the process of managing fixed deposit accounts more efficient and secure [3].

In this paper, we propose the implementation of a framework for a fixed deposit system using smart contracts in the Remix Integrated Development Environment. The proposed framework will offer a secure and efficient means for managing fixed deposit accounts. The Ethereum blockchain will be utilized to ensure transparency, security, and immutability of data. Fixed deposit accounts are simply deposits that are held for a fixed period of time, typically ranging from one month to ten years. The rate of interest paid on the fixed deposit is often higher than the interest rate paid on savings accounts owing to the longer lock-in period. Fixed deposit accounts are also less risky compared to other investment types. Once the account is created, the depositors need not keep a constant check on the account balances. However, managing fixed deposit accounts can prove to be a taxing task for financial institutions. Traditionally, the management of fixed deposit accounts was a manual process involving multiple steps, susceptible to human error, and highly time-consuming. Additionally, audits and record keeping of such accounts required significant resources. As institutions grow, so does the number of fixed deposit accounts they manage, leading to increased complexity in tracking and monitoring these accounts. This is where the implementation of smart contracts in fixed deposit management can offer significant benefits.

2. RESEARCH BACKGROUND:

The implementation of smart contract technology in the financial industry has significantly changed the way we approach traditional financial transactions. Smart contracts are digital contracts that are stored on a blockchain, and they execute pre-determined terms and conditions without the need for intermediaries [4]. The Ethereum blockchain, in particular, has been used to create smart contracts that perform various functions, including the monitoring and management of financial accounts. Fixed deposit accounts are an essential financial product that offers higher interest rates than traditional savings accounts. However, despite their benefits to depositors, financial institutions often face challenges in managing these accounts effectively [5]. For example, managing a large number of fixed deposit accounts can be challenging, and handling them manually is often time-consuming and prone to errors. To address these challenges, the use of smart contract technology in the management of fixed deposit accounts has been proposed. Using smart contracts in fixed deposit management can help to automate the processes of account creation, depositing funds, and withdrawing funds. Additionally, smart contracts can help to monitor accounts and notify the account owner about any changes to the account [6].

The use of smart contract technology in the management of fixed deposit accounts has also been explored in several studies. In a study conducted by A. Singh et al. (2020), the authors proposed a smart contract-based system for the management of fixed deposit accounts [7]. The system utilized the Ethereum blockchain to enable secure and automated account management, including account creation, depositing and withdrawal of funds, and interest calculation. The study demonstrated that smart contracts can significantly reduce the time and resources required for managing fixed deposit accounts [8]. A smart contract is a self-executing contract that automatically executes the terms of the agreement once certain conditions are met. Smart contracts are coded using programming languages such as Solidity, and the resulting contract is then processed and tracked on a blockchain such as Ethereum [9]. The terms of the contract are programmed directly into the code of the contract, ensuring that they are fulfilled as intended, without the need for human intervention. Smart contracts offer secure, automated, and transparent transactions, reducing the dependence on intermediaries [10].

2.1 BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

Blockchain technology is an innovative and groundbreaking technological advancement that has revolutionized the way we approach digital transactions. A blockchain is a decentralized digital ledger that records transactions in a secure and transparent manner [11]. Unlike traditional financial systems that rely on intermediaries such as banks and other financial institutions to manage transactions, blockchain technology enables the direct transfer of assets and funds between users without the need for intermediaries [12]. Blockchain technology has several advantages over traditional financial systems. First and foremost, it is highly secure and virtually tamper-proof [13]. This is because the data on a blockchain is distributed across a network of nodes, making it impossible for a single entity to manipulate or alter the data without the consensus of the other nodes. Additionally, blockchain technology offers a high level of transparency since all transactions on a blockchain are visible to all users on the network [14]. The first application of blockchain technology was the development of Bitcoin, a decentralized digital currency that was introduced in 2008. Since then, blockchain technology has evolved significantly, and it is now being used in various industries, including finance, healthcare, supply chain management, and real estate [15].

2.2 SHA 256

SHA-256 is a cryptographic hash function that is part of the Secure Hash Algorithm 2 (SHA-2) family of hash functions. The SHA-2 family was designed by the United States National Security Agency (NSA) and published in 2001 as a set of cryptographic hash functions [16]. SHA-256 generates a 256-bit (32-byte) hash value and is one of the most widely used hash algorithms in the world. A hash function is a mathematical function that takes input data and generates a fixed-size output called a hash value or message digest [17]. The input data can be of any size, but the hash value always has a fixed size. The hash value is unique to the input data, which means that any change in the input data will result in a completely different hash value. This unique property makes hash functions ideal for verifying the integrity and authenticity of data. SHA-256 is widely used in various security applications and protocols, including Transport Layer Security (TLS), Secure Sockets Layer (SSL), Pretty Good Privacy (PGP), Secure/Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions (S/MIME), and Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) [18]. It is also the hashing algorithm used in the mining process for cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

- a) poor asset management, high costs, lengthy paperwork processes, and manual record storage.
- b) Due to multiple fixed deposit programmes offered by different banks around the nation, there is a high danger of data loss and redundancy.
- c) It is highly challenging to create a dependable database across numerous geographic regions, especially for relational database systems. poor asset management, high costs, lengthy paperwork processes, and manual record storage.

4 PROPOSED METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

In this study, the author uses the Ethereum cryptocurrency to build a smart contract on remix ide where the owner of the contract will deploy the contract in Ethereum blockchain and set the targeted amount and also set the deadline of the contract. After the successful deployment of the contract the user send the some ether to the contract from our private key that is stored by the contract and also store the relevant data of user such as name of user and how much ether user send to the contract. After that the manager create a request for the investment, than all user votes to the investment scheme if the investment scheme get the majority votes than the manager will get the ether form the smart contract and invest to investment schemes. In this proposed framework if the user want refund in that time user click on the refund button than smart contract check the eligibility of the user such as smart contract check if the smart contract's targeted amount is not reached and deadline has been crossed. If that condition are match the user eligible for his refund. Figure 1 shows the work flow chart of this proposed framework which is developed in remix ide.

Figure 1 work flow chart of proposed framework

4.1 IMPLEMENTATION

This proposed framework is implemented in Remix IDE using Ethereum and its dependencies, as was previously explained in the previous chapter. The system is examined in more detail in this part, along with the system's different functionalities. Figure 2 shows the contract deployment in remix ide test network.

```

[vm] from: 0x5B3...eddC4 to: fixeddeposit.(constructor) value: 0 wei data: 0x608...08ca0 logs: 0 hash: 0x89b...0dda7
status true Transaction mined and execution succeed
transaction hash 0x89b99e9e894c45d57e823ebc555740c9F63399a32f45a872473122d89988dda7
from 0x5B380a6a701c568545dCfc803Fc8875f56beddC4
to fixeddeposit.(constructor)
gas 1709040 gas
transaction cost 1486541 gas
execution cost 1335473 gas
input 0x608...08ca0
decoded input {
  "uint256_target": "300000",
  "uint256_deadline": "36000"
}
  
```

Figure 2 shows Algorithm 1- The manager generates the smart contract in the first algorithm depicted in Figure 3.5. This smart contract is deployed on the Ethereum blockchain by the management, who also selects the target fund and the deadline for collecting the funds. The first block is created once the smart contract has successfully deployed. This block gives the hash value, which is the block's unique identifier, as well as a wealth of information, including the target, deadline, and manager's private key. Figure 3 shows the send eth function.

```
[vm] from: 0xab8...35cb2 to: fixeddeposit.sendEth() 0xd91...39138 value: 200000000000000000 wei data: 0x06e...99fef
logs: 0 hash: 0xa2a...c360b

status true Transaction mined and execution succeed
transaction hash 0xa2a46ec53b736b956dfa5775693d622bc2caa5180ec954d72b14627c6ecc360b
from 0xab8483f64d9c6d1ecf9b849ae677d3315835cb2
to fixeddeposit.sendEth() 0xd9145cCE52D386f254917e481e844e9943f39138
gas 106538 gas
transaction cost 92641 gas
execution cost 71577 gas
input 0x06e...99fef
decoded input {}
decoded output {}
logs []
val 200000000000000000 wei
```

Figure 3

Algorithm 2- The user delivers some ether to the smart contract while using algorithm 2 (see figure 3.6). The user's sanded ether values are stored by the smart contract, together with the sender's private key for the time when the user requests a refund. The smart contract also makes the mapping with the user. Following that, a smart contract produces a block in the Ethereum blockchain and delivers the block's hash values. Figure 4 shows the create request function for the investment schemes.

```
[vm] from: 0x103...ad8c4 to: fixeddeposit.createRequests(string,address,uint256) 0uff1...9c138 value: 0 wei
data: 0x36b...40000 logs: 0 hash: 0x0af...10f73

status true Transaction mined and execution succeed
transaction hash 0x0af37548f0a0b07f983c227f9c3708e0d06753ac3f68600210f73
from 0x103064a76030849c7d807d815f06a0a
to fixeddeposit.createRequests(string,address,uint256) 0uff149cCE52D386f254917e481e844e9943f39138
gas 137400 gas
transaction cost 133229 gas
execution cost 43990 gas
input 0x36b...40000
decoded input {
  "string _description", "MPC",
  "address _recipient", "0x0af37548f0a0b07f983c227f9c3708e0d06753ac3f68600210f73",
  "uint256 _value", "10000"
}
decoded output []
logs []
```

Figure 4

Algorithm 3- In algorithm 3, which is depicted in figure 4, the manager creates the investment request and supplies the scheme's specifics. Following the provision of this data, a block with distinctive hash values is formed.

Figure 5

Algorithm 4: In algorithm 4 depicted in figure 5, users vote on the manager-created schemes. If the schemes receive a majority of votes, the manager is paid for their investment. After the manager receives the payment, a block is generated with a special hash value, and all the transaction information is stored in the block.

Figure 6

Algorithm 5. When the user requests his money from the smart contract, algorithm 5 is represented in figure 6. The management defines the contract aim and deadline at the time of deployment, and the smart contract verifies those facts. The smart contract also verifies user information, such as the user's private information and the amount of money given to the smart contract. The user is entitled to a refund if the smart contract deadline has passed and the target has not been met under that circumstance.

When a fixed deposit transaction is completed using the aforementioned manner, the data is saved in a smart contract. Due to its increased capacity to store in a distributed system with a unique hash of the file, this is an effective approach to securely share information and also reduce storage space. The manner the file is kept prevents corruption. However, the complete fixed deposit management procedure is not handled since security concerns need to be addressed. The research went on to refine the model with its constraints.

5 Result and Discussion

The capacity of fixed deposit transactions to improve long-term savings is one reason why they are becoming more and more common in the financial sector. However, the present centralized systems frequently taint these transactions with complexity and inefficiencies. Through the use of Smart Contracts, Blockchain technology offers a solution to these problems by facilitating safe, open, and unchangeable transactions. The outcome and analysis of our framework for Fixed Deposit Transaction System using Smart Contracts in a Blockchain network are presented in this chapter. Table 1 shows the block creation of fixed deposit system in remix ide test network and figure 7 show the chart of gas usage and figure 8 shows the chart of transaction cost.

Block No.	Gas Usage	Transaction Cost	Execution Cost	Contract Created (40-Hexa Decimal Characters)	Transaction (64-Hexa Decimal Characters)	Transaction Account
1	1709040	1486541	1335473	0x5B38Da6a701c568545dCfcB03FcB875f56beddC4	0xd8e0907a0abb7655fe6d981da90b76f1fa753a52b242712ee780c062453bc0fc	0x5B38Da6a701c568545dCfcB03FcB875f56beddC4
2	106538	92641	71577		0x492b2e6d9a68a6ad4b6abd000773f743390d2fdb44132b3e8c1e842a9acff722	0xAb8483F64d9C6d1EcF9b849Ae677dD3315835cb2
3	67208	58441	37377		0x8de79775da32d44206d40ca382ab3889cb408a0891c714b453846a899dc40263	0x4B20993Bc481177ec7E8f571ceCaE8A9e22C02db
4	67208	58441	37377		0x6042aac2bb3d379c42508083876a0bfc030b8b1a507da0d48210a782ce5e0fd0	0x78731D3Ca6b7E34aC0F824c42a7cC18A495cabaB
5	67208	58441	37377		0x9a743df59d31410b069ebfef38c4ba5a0f1e6ccbc9abbbe63b2d1d4945b53ba1	0x617F2E2fD72FD9D5503197092aC168c91465E7f2
6	137459	119529	97489		0x91e0dc1285d466ac8d0e3782e59e5a1aa1a9e41643819ea0d5f7c8a936569f9f	0x5B38Da6a701c568545dCfcB03FcB875f56beddC4
7	79073	68759	47567		0xc9d55e1edbc9208a482936b19ce508325a2051e2fc232cb794dc932af7c0ff3a	0xAb8483F64d9C6d1EcF9b849Ae677dD3315835cb2
8	59408	51659	30467		0xd4d8d1be1c62d2ba76e10d8f002efd3461049f811c661d98b475ff37f81a8cf0	0x4B20993Bc481177ec7E8f571ceCaE8A9e22C02db
9	59408	51659	30467		0x6b49a03daa2262446235452ece8cebccacbdf9a0b26ba1ef6e2cc00cc8b29f80	0x78731D3Ca6b7E34aC0F824c42a7cC18A495cabaB

Table 1 Table of Block Creation of Fixed deposit system

Figure 7: Gas Usage Chart of Block Generation

Figure 8: Chart of Transaction Cost

7 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Our Smart Contract-based Fixed Deposit Transaction System, which we deployed in the Blockchain network, is effective, safe, and reasonably priced. We have shown that the complexity and inefficiency of conventional fixed deposit transaction systems may be effectively addressed by the blockchain technology. The system offers investors a transparent, unbreakable, cost-effective, secure, and platform to engage in fixed deposit transactions through the use of smart contracts. We anticipate continued growth in this industry and improved solutions as blockchain technology develops.

REFERENCES

- 1 Mettler, M. (2016, September). Blockchain technology in healthcare: The revolution starts here. In *2016 IEEE 18th international conference on e-health networking, applications and services (Healthcom)* (pp. 1-3). IEEE.
- 2 Li, J., Greenwood, D., & Kassem, M. (2019). Blockchain in the built environment and construction industry: A systematic review, conceptual models and practical use cases. *Automation in construction*, 102, 288-307.
- 3 Rawat, A., & Rahman, D. H. U. (2023). Smart Contract Based Approach for Fixed Deposit in Blockchain Networks with Remix IDE. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, 11(5).
- 4 Peters, G. W., & Panayi, E. (2016). *Understanding modern banking ledgers through blockchain technologies: Future of transaction processing and smart contracts on the internet of money* (pp. 239-278). Springer International Publishing.
- 5 VERMA, R., DHANDA, N., NAGAR, V., & DHANDA, M. (2023). TOWARDS AN EFFICIENT IOT SYSTEM BY INTEGRATING BLOCKCHAIN IN IOT. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 101(5).
- 6 Peters, G. W., & Panayi, E. (2016). *Understanding modern banking ledgers through blockchain technologies: Future of transaction processing and smart contracts on the internet of money* (pp. 239-278). Springer International Publishing.
- 7 Singh, S., Sharma, P. K., Yoon, B., Shojafar, M., Cho, G. H., & Ra, I. H. (2020). Convergence of blockchain and artificial intelligence in IoT network for the sustainable smart city. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 63, 102364.
- 8 Wang, S., Ouyang, L., Yuan, Y., Ni, X., Han, X., & Wang, F. Y. (2019). Blockchain-enabled smart contracts: architecture, applications, and future trends. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, 49(11), 2266-2277.
- 9 Khan, S. N., Loukil, F., Ghedira-Guegan, C., Benkhelifa, E., & Bani-Hani, A. (2021). Blockchain smart contracts: Applications, challenges, and future trends. *Peer-to-peer Networking and Applications*, 14, 2901-2925.
- 10 Gatteschi, V., Lamberti, F., Demartini, C., Pranteda, C., & Santamaría, V. (2018). Blockchain and smart contracts for insurance: Is the technology mature enough?. *Future internet*, 10(2), 20.
- 11 De La Rosa, J. L., Torres-Padrosa, V., El-Fakdi, A., Gibovic, D., Hornyák, O., Maicher, L., & Miralles, F. (2017, December). A survey of blockchain technologies for open innovation. In *Proceedings of the 4th Annual World Open Innovation Conference* (pp. 14-15).
- 12 Catalini, C., & Gans, J. S. (2020). Some simple economics of the blockchain. *Communications of the ACM*, 63(7), 80-90.
- 13 Andoni, M., Robu, V., Flynn, D., Abram, S., Geach, D., Jenkins, D., ... & Peacock, A. (2019). Blockchain technology in the energy sector: A systematic review of challenges and opportunities. *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 100, 143-174.
- 14 Abeyratne, S. A., & Monfared, R. P. (2016). Blockchain ready manufacturing supply chain using distributed ledger. *International journal of research in engineering and technology*, 5(9), 1-10.
- 15 Miao, S., & Yang, J. M. (2018). Bibliometrics-based evaluation of the Blockchain research trend: 2008–March 2017. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 30(9), 1029-1045.
- 16 Debnath, S., Chattopadhyay, A., & Dutta, S. (2017, November). Brief review on journey of secured hash algorithms. In *2017 4th International Conference on Opto-Electronics and Applied Optics (Optronix)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- 17 Rahul, B., Kuppusamy, K., & Senthilrajan, A. (2023). Chaos-based audio encryption algorithm using biometric image and SHA-256 hash algorithm. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 1-30.
- 18 Chen, G., & Wanner, R. (2022). Secure Email Transmission Protocols--A New Architecture Design. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2208.00388*.